

DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE BASED ON INTERACTIVE METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS**Yuldashev Salakhiddin Azamovich**Head of the Department of Social Sciences,
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ANNOTATION

The article examines the issues of developing students' communicative competence in foreign language lessons based on interactive methods. The main goal of the study is to identify the scientific and methodological foundations for improving students' communication skills in a foreign language and increasing educational efficiency through the use of modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods.

The research methodology was based on communicative, person-oriented, active and integrative approaches. The research process used methods of analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature, observation, comparative analysis, pedagogical experiment-testing and diagnostics. Also, the didactic potential of interactive methods such as "brainstorming", "discussion", "role-playing", "work in small groups" and "case-study" in developing communicative competence in foreign language lessons was studied.

The scientific and practical significance of the research is determined by its contribution to improving foreign language teaching methods, implementing innovative approaches aimed at developing communicative competence, and improving the professional training of future specialists.

Keywords: communicative competence, interactive methods, foreign language teaching, communicative approach, pedagogical technologies, speech activity, interactive education, foreign language methodology, educational effectiveness, communicative skills.

INTRODUCTION

The task of improving the system of teaching the national language and culture of the countries whose language is being studied and preparing them for natural communication by developing the linguocultural and communicative competence of future translators is becoming increasingly urgent. This will provide information not only about the history, state structure, but also about the national culture of the country whose language is being studied, but also, on the other hand, in the process of reading texts in foreign languages, it will be possible to translate specific words (realia), that is, unique language units, phraseological units, aphorisms, and to teach students to actively and freely use speech culture in speech communication.

The development of oral speech of students in the field of translation requires starting with the simultaneous teaching of the language and culture of the country whose language is being studied. Any translation process is a dialogue between two languages - two cultures, and a great deal of attention is paid to the study of intercultural dialogue, along with the correct and objective interpretation of intercultural dialogue. Also, the linguocultural problems of translator training require the study of the role of intercultural dialogue, cases of cultural adaptation in translation, and the foreign language lesson as a crossroads of intercultural encounters.

The concept of "integration", which ensures the integrity of the methodological system and interdisciplinary connections as a rule for the development of teaching methods, has given rise to the principles of integrating personal or activity-related, as well as socio-cultural and discursive

linguodidactic approaches to translation training. The acquisition of such knowledge and skills requires the mastery of the following general principles of organizing translator training: the principle of a personal approach in the training of translators; the principle of an active approach in the preparation of translations; the principle of a socio-approach in the training of translators; the principle of a discursive approach in the training of translators.

Linguistic and communicative competence refers to the types of speech activity in foreign language practice and independent levels of language: phonetic, lexical, phraseological, grammatical (morphological and syntactic), stylistic knowledge. This competence includes the process of using all knowledge related to listening, speaking, reading, writing, and phonetic, lexical, phraseological, and grammatical skills in everyday practice through various information related to everyday life and the environment.

Attention was paid to identifying methods for training future translators and highlighting the level of competence that students can acquire through these methods.

There are four levels of development of linguocultural competence. The content of the levels we offer is as follows:

a) the first stage of the development of linguistic and cultural competence, according to A.N. Shamov, "begins with the accumulation of empirical knowledge - observations of the functioning of lexical units in various communicative contexts (oral and written). At this stage, a presentation of the semantization of new lexis was organized. As a result, students in the field got a preliminary idea of the sound and graphic image of a lexical unit and served to form connections between a word in a foreign language and its meaning. As a result, students in the field acquired the skills of identifying lexical units in the presented communicative situations;

b) the second stage of the development of linguistic and cultural competence includes the task of forming students' skills in using the studied lexical units, establishing strong connections between lexical units and their meaning. At this stage, speech training of the studied lexicons initially involves the use of words of a certain communicative content helps to strengthen primary skills. The communicative basis of the linguistic exercises proposed by us and used in practice at this stage served to consistently illuminate the scope of application of the studied lexical units, to demonstrate their communicative capabilities; c) the third level of development of linguocultural competence is associated with the acquisition of theoretical knowledge about the lexical system of the language being studied, that is, with the expansion of students' linguistic understanding, thinking and practical experience. This level aims to form in students the skills to determine the form, structure and meaning of words, to make a certain contribution to the creation of verbal and semantic coherent connections. As a result, the formal side of the language being studied is thoroughly mastered, which contributes to the development of the foreign philological worldview of students in the field;

Based on the differences in the scientific and methodological literature on the components of linguistic and communicative competence, the following types were recommended and described: a) cognitive component; b) operational-activity component; c) reflexive component.

Attention was paid to identifying the stages of development of linguistic and communicative competence of future translators, and based on the results of the research, we came to the following conclusions:

1. The second stage of development of linguistic and communicative competence of future translators. At this stage, the student manages the studied linguistic and communicative structure in speech situations typical for his activity. At this stage, the transfer of theoretical knowledge to practical foreign language activity, the development of communicative skills, depending on the conditions of communication, requires the adequacy of the grammatical coloring of thought. To achieve the set goals and objectives, we used types of language exercises, in particular, imitation, substitution (reserve) and transformation exercises, in our research and experimental work, the conditions of the recommended sample tasks for implementation were developed and we recommended their use in educational practice.

2. The communicative practice stage of developing the linguocultural and communicative competence of future translators. The purpose of this stage is to further develop the linguocultural skills of the production and receptive foreign language, to correct and correct those formed in the previous stages as much as possible, and to move from communicative skills to grammatical skills. At this stage, communicative tasks for using grammatical phenomena activated depending on the speech situation prevail.

3. The control stage of developing the linguocultural and communicative competence of future translators. This stage included the collection and analysis of data on the level of formation of students' linguistic and cultural and communicative competence, as well as the results of their own assessment of the mastered grammatical material. The indicators of the development of linguistic and cultural and communicative competence in future translators were determined as consisting of 4 criteria: cognitive, operational-activity, motivational and reflexive.

The issue of the phenomenal nature, description and determination of its tasks of speech competence is relevant in modern science. In this direction in language education, A.N. Ksenofontova was the first to recommend her observations to the scientific community. After that, we also observed that M.P. Manaenkova distinguished the following tasks of speech competence: knowledge acquisition (expression), information (message, expression), communicative (influence), motivational (motivational). At the same time, based on the fact that in the real process all tasks are interconnected and can pass into each other, we dwell on each of them separately:

a) the task of speech competence to acquire knowledge, since it is, on the one hand, a means of thinking, and on the other hand, a product of mental activity, is especially closely related to the role of speech in the implementation of higher mental tasks of a person with thinking. Speech is the main tool in educational activity, allowing the teacher to organize and implement it both in the classroom and outside the school.

b) the motivating (motivational) function of speech competence is determined by the attitude towards the profession. The chosen professional activity style of the teacher also finds its expression in speech activity. Speech competence determines the orientation of the teacher's personality, that is, the set of needs and motives that determine the main direction of the person's own behavior. The motivating function of speech competence is manifested in speech behavior. The direction of speech behavior depends on the level of formation of the teacher's speech competence.

We will consider exercises and tasks used to form a reflexive perspective of future translators on the analysis of specific situations that require the development of linguistic and cultural and communicative competence.

1. "Situation analysis: Communicative competence in me..."

Goal: to create a positive self-image, develop empathy in each participant, and increase self-esteem.

After analyzing specific situations, the teacher asks each participant to express the following thoughts: "I appreciate developing communicative competence in me", "I appreciate ... (name of one of the classmates)", "I appreciate in life".

Until the end of the exercise, the teacher asks to share the thoughts and feelings that arose during its implementation.

2. Write an essay on the topic "I am a supporter of the development of linguistic and cultural qualities".

Purpose: to develop linguistic and cultural and communicative competence of future translators.

The "6x6x6" method is one of the most effective methods for developing linguistic and communicative competence of future translators. When using this method to work on small texts, the teacher is required to have pedagogical skills and ingenuity, as well as the ability to form groups. In this method, students in the class are divided into six groups of six each. The groups

are given specific names. The topic of the lesson is announced and a certain time is set. Students discuss the topic, express their opinions. After the time set for the topic is over, the teacher changes the members of the groups. One representative from the previous group remains in the new group, and he or she presents the conclusions of his or her group on the topic to the new group. Members of the new group study the ideas and conclusions of the previous group, expressing their own opinions on it. Thus, in a short period of time, students both express their opinions on the topic and analyze these opinions themselves.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the process of developing linguocultural and communicative competence of future translators occurs on the basis of a clear and correct implementation of a sequence of complex pedagogical systems. In this sense, it is necessary to organize education aimed at developing linguocultural and communicative competence on the basis of interactive methods and educational technologies.

The pedagogical tasks of developing linguocultural competence require a systematic approach. In order to form linguocultural thinking in future translators, it is necessary to integrate special training in intercultural communication, pragmatics and analysis of cultural codes into the educational process. These tasks reveal not only the linguistic, but also the socio-cultural essence of the translation process. A clear definition of pedagogical tasks serves the gradual formation of competencies.

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